

ORGANIZATION OF PERSON-CENTERED EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation. In the context of globalization, education plays an important role in the comprehensive development of the individual, in the formation of the qualities of perfection and a qualified specialist. Today's fast-paced period requires equipping students with short-term and reliable information, creating the necessary conditions for them to master the basics of various disciplines. In modern conditions, the educational process is required to focus on the development, socialization of the individual and the development of independent, critical, creative thinking skills. Education that is able to demonstrate these capabilities in itself is called person-centered education.

Keywords: personality, education, person-centered education and its types, innovative forms of education, innovative methods, innovative tools, educational projects, portfolio, student portfolio

This implies that the learning environment is adapted to the student's capabilities. According to him, the educational environment, pedagogical conditions, the process of education and upbringing as a whole implies the realization of the student's personal potential, the development of abilities, ensuring personal development, enrichment of thinking and worldview. This type of education serves to cultivate in students such qualities as independence, initiative, responsibility, as well as the ability to think independently, creatively and critically. In the organization of this type of education, educators are required to approach each student as individually as possible, to respect his personality, to trust him. In addition, the participants of the process of person-centered education express the need to create favorable pedagogical conditions for mutual learning in the form of teacher-student or student-student, student-student group, student-student community, personal development. The educator must strictly adhere to a number of conditions when using person-centered forms of learning in the learning process. These requirements include:

- be able to see each student as a separate, unique person;
- respect for the student;
- be able to correctly assess the mental state of the student; - take into account the wishes and interests of the student;
- be tolerant of each student;
- Confidence in the strengths, abilities and aspirations of the student;

- create a comfortable learning environment for each student;
- creating opportunities for students to work independently or in small groups;
- To teach students to independently monitor their activities, determine the effectiveness of their activities, analyze the factors of success and the consequences of mistakes;
- not to put pressure on any student in the educational process;
- not to exaggerate the shortcomings of the individual student;
- If the student's inability to acquire knowledge is observed in the course of educational behavior, then to determine the reasons for this, without drawing any conclusions;
- on the basis of the identified reasons to eliminate the situation when the student is not able to acquire knowledge without damaging the honor and dignity, to behave rudely;
- to be able to create an "environment of success" for each student in the educational process; - to help each student to succeed in education; - to develop the student's abilities, to help him develop as a person;

Person-centered education is part of the student education system

- The ability of each student to earn the respect and trust of the teacher does not mean adaptation, but rather the creation of the necessary conditions for his full development, maturity as a person, taking into account his individual characteristics. This type of education should create the necessary conditions for students to develop themselves, to acquire independent knowledge, to fully express their inner potential, abilities, to increase cognitive activity. In the process of person-centered learning, students will have the opportunity to develop a creative, critical approach to the study of educational material, the ability to promote new ideas, justify them, defend their views, find effective solutions to problematic situations. The use of various active methods by the educator in the educational process of an innovative nature serves to develop students, to further increase their abilities.

In particular:

- problem research;
- Carrying out small researches;
- debate; - debate;
- heuristic conversation;
- work in small groups, b. In organizing their classes, educators should pay special attention to ensuring that educational information is based on the

knowledge, skills, abilities and experience of students, so that they have the opportunity to engage, think, and take a creative approach.

In the educational process by teachers:

- effective, targeted use of various forms, methods, tools and technologies;
- to allow students to independently choose methods for performing educational tasks;
- Ensuring that the student works in pairs, small groups and teams;
- Focusing on the design of lessons not only improves the quality and effectiveness of teaching. Most importantly, educators need to pay attention to the fact that training is not only informative, but also developmental. It is also one of the most important features of a person-centered education to allow students to express themselves independently (albeit incorrectly) on the subject under discussion.

The use of the following in the learning process is another sign of person-centered learning:

- creative assignments;
- Tasks that require a creative approach;
- problematic situations;
- role and business games;
- debate, debate;
- Competitions

In modern conditions, it is advisable to use innovative forms of education in order to strengthen the learning activities of students, improve the quality and effectiveness of teaching. Today, practical games, problem-based learning, interactive learning, modulkredit system, distance learning, blended learning and master classes are recognized as innovative forms of education. Practical games used in educational practice are in themselves didactic in nature, which is why they are often referred to as “didactic games”. Throughout all periods of human historical development, play has been recognized as the first and most important type of subject activity. Consequently, along with important types of personal activities - work, study, play also plays an important role in its formation and development. Through life, the life experience accumulated by the older generation, the acquired knowledge, the basics of lifestyle and social relations, cultural values have been consistently passed on to the younger generation. The game has the features of educating, developing, educating the individual. Due to its existing features, games have long been one of the important foundations of folk pedagogy. Direct games serve to educate children

spiritually, morally, mentally, physically and aesthetically by helping them develop cognition, intuition, memory, thinking, speech. "A preschooler is prepared to study and work in play activities. As you get older, the role of the game diminishes a bit. The educational value of games will be maintained throughout the child's life."

REFERENCES:

1. Avliyakov N.X., Musaeva N.N. Modular learning technologies. - T.: "Science and Technology" Publishing House, 2007. - 97 p.
2. Ganieva M.A., Fayzullaeva D.M. A set of pedagogical technologies of case-study teaching / Met.qo'll. From the series "Innovative technologies in the system of secondary, vocational education." - T.: TDIU, 2013. - 95 p.
3. Ishmuhamedov R., Abduqodirov A., Pardaev A. Innovative technologies in education / Practical recommendations. - T.: "Iste'dod" fund, 2008. - 180 p.
4. Olimov Q.T. Pedagogical technologies. - T.: "Science and Technology" Publishing House, 2011. - 275 p.
5. Ruzieva D., Usmonboeva M., Holiqova Z. Interactive methods: essence and application / Method. - T.: DTPU named after Nizami, 2013. - 115 p.

